

An annotated checklist of Tenuipalpidae (Acari: Trombidiformes) of Ukraine

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Zhovnerchuk, O.V., Bondareva, L.M. & Chumak, P.Ya. An annotated checklist of Tenuipalpidae (Acari: Trombidiformes) of Ukraine.

— The previously published species of false spider mites known for the territory of Ukraine are revised. The list of Tenuipalpidae of Ukraine now includes 32 species of six genera. The genera with the highest number of species are *Brevipalpus* Donnadieu, 1875 and *Cenopalpus* Pritchard & Baker, 1958. Most of the finds (25 species) are recorded only in the southern regions of Ukraine.

Key words: false spider mites, species diversity, distribution, Ukraine.

Жовнерчук, О.В., Бондарєва, Л.М. і Чумак, П.Я. Анотований чек-лист кліщів родини Tenuipalpidae (Acari: Trombidiformes) України. — Критично переглянуто зареєстровані раніше види кліщів-плоскотілок (Acari, Tenuipalpidae) з території України. Список тєнуіпальпід України налічує 32 види з шести родів. Найбільша кількість видів належить до родів *Brevipalpus* Donnadieu, 1875 та *Cenopalpus* Pritchard & Baker, 1958. Більшість знахідок (25 видів) зафіксовано лише в південних областях України.

Ключові слова: кліщі-плоскотілки, видове різноманіття, поширення, Україна.

Introduction

Mites of the family Tenuipalpidae are widespread all over the world. The family includes 1013 species of 39 genera (Mesa *et al.*, 2009; Beard *et al.*, 2012; Castro *et al.*, 2020). Some of these mites can severely damage plants by direct feeding on the contents of their cells, and also contribute to the transmission of plant viruses (Mesa *et al.*, 2009; Beard *et al.*, 2012; Castro *et al.*, 2020).

Although the false spider mites are economically important, this group is not extensively studied in Ukraine. The most systemic and large-scale study of Tenuipalpidae mites in Ukraine was conducted by the scientists of the Nikitsky Botanical Garden, National Academy of Agrarian Sciences of Ukraine (then U.S.S.R.). However, they have studied only the territory of the Southern coast of Crimea (Livschitz & Mitrofanov, 1967, 1973; Mitrofanov *et al.*, 1975; Mitrofanov & Strunkova, 1979). The monograph of Mitrofanov and Strunkova (1979) has become a milestone in the studies of Tenuipalpidae mites of Crimea. In that work, 22 species were noted for Ukraine. All of them

except *Brevipalpus lewisi* McGregor, 1949 were observed only in Crimea. The other territory of Ukraine remains terra incognita in the study of false spider mites. There are but a few fragmentary data on the finds of *Cenopalpus pulcher* (Canestrini & Fanzago 1876) in the Southern regions (Livschitz, 1964) in the zone of mixed forests of Ukraine (Voitenko, 1969), and in orchards of steppe and forest-steppe (Kruglikov, 1985; Pogrebnyak, 1998). In the northern regions of Ukraine, *C. pulcher* mites are infrequently found and not very harmful. In the southern regions, the mass reproduction of that species is periodically observed. The widespread species *Brevipalpus obovatus* Donnadieu, 1875 was found in Ukraine for the first time as a pest of greenhouse plants (Voitenko, 1969). Later, several more species of false spider mites were observed on plants of greenhouses of botanical gardens in Ukraine (Chumak, 2000, 2003, 2004).

Recently, two species of the genus *Pentamerismus* were found in Kyiv: *P. taxi* on yew (Bondareva & Chumak, 2018) and *P. oregonensis* on juniper (Bondareva &

Chumak, 2020). Earlier, mites of the genus *Pentamerismus* were recorded only in the southern regions of Ukraine (Mitrofanov & Strunkova, 1979).

Most finds of Tenuipalpidae are from the South of Ukraine, where the climate is sub-tropical, favoring the false spider mites. On the contrary, a few species were recorded from the other territory of Ukraine with moderate continental climate.

Some information on the diversity of the false spider mites in Ukraine is summarized by Mesa *et al.* (2009), with only 20 species of them recorded from Ukraine. The authors obviously omitted all the works mentioning the finds of tenuipalpid.

In this work, we fulfill this gap and provide a complete list of Ukrainian tenuipalpid and comprehensive information on their distribution.

While preparing this checklist, the data from the database of Tenuipalpidae (Castro *et al.*, 2020) with 30 species from Ukraine, are also analyzed here. *Brevipalpus borealis* (Mitrofanov *et al.*, 1975) is listed in the database as “Ukrainian”, while it was actually found in Latvia. *Cenopalpus thelycraniae* (Livschitz & Mitrofanov, 1967) was found in Georgia rather than Ukraine (Livschitz & Mitrofanov, 1967; Mitrofanov & Strunkova, 1979). Four other species recorded on the territory of Ukraine are absent in the database: *Aegyptobia wainsteini* (Bagdasarian, 1962), *Brevipalpus lewisi* McGregor, 1949, *Brevipalpus phoenicis* (Geijskes, 1939) and *Brevipalpus thelycraniae* Livschitz & Mitrofanov, 1967. To date, the Tenuipalpidae of Ukraine is comprised of 32 species of six genera according to the published data. This is the first checklist about Tenuipalpidae from Ukraine.

Material and Methods

The list of species is prepared based on all of the analyzed and accessible publications which mention the finds of false spider mites in Ukraine. The locations of these finds and the host plants are presented, with the level of pest harmfulness when it has been noted. The names of host plants are given according to GBIF (Global Biodiversity Information Facility).

List of the Tenuipalpidae of Ukraine

Tenuipalpidae Berlese, 1913

Aegyptobia Sayed, 1950

Aegyptobia beglarovi Livschitz & Mitrofanov, 1967

Livschitz & Mitrofanov (1967, 1973), Mitrofanov *et al.* (1975), Mitrofanov & Strunkova (1979).

Distribution in Ukraine. Crimea.

Host plants. *Juniperus oxycedrus* L., *J. communis* L., *Juniperus* sp.

Notes: rarely severely damages host plants.

Aegyptobia exarata Livschitz & Mitrofanov, 1967

Livschitz & Mitrofanov (1967), Mitrofanov & Strunkova (1979).

Distribution in Ukraine. Crimea.

Host plants. *Artemisia* sp.

Aegyptobia wainsteini Bagdasarian, 1962

Livschitz & Mitrofanov (1973), Mitrofanov *et al.* (1975), Mitrofanov & Strunkova (1979).

Distribution in Ukraine. Crimea.

Host plant. *Juniperus* sp.

Notes: rarely causes several damage to host plants.

Brevipalpus Donnadieu, 1875

Brevipalpus cuneatus (Canestrini & Fanzago, 1876)

Livschitz & Mitrofanov (1967, 1973), Mitrofanov & Strunkova (1979: *Hystripalpus cuneatus*).

Distribution in Ukraine. Crimea.

Host plant. *Hedera taurica* Carr.

Notes: causes mosaic patterns on leaves.

Brevipalpus lewisi McGregor, 1949

Livschitz & Mitrofanov (1973), Mitrofanov & Strunkova (1979: *Hystripalpus lewisi*), Chumak (2000, 2003: *Hystripalpus lewisi*).

Distribution in Ukraine. Odesa Region, also in greenhouses of Kyiv and Odesa.

Host plants. *Arachis* sp., *Aster* sp., *Catalpa* sp., *Citrus* sp., *Ephedra* sp., *Geranium* sp., *Juglans regia* L., *Myrtus* sp., *Pistacia* sp., *Rosa* sp., *Vitis* sp.

Notes: often severely damages host plants.

Brevipalpus obovatus Donnadieu, 1875

Livschitz & Mitrofanov (1967), Vojtenko (1969), Livschitz *et al.* (1972), Livschitz & Mitrofanov (1973), Mitrofanov & Strunkova (1979), Tereznikova & Chumak (1989), Chumak (2000, 2003, 2004a, b).

Distribution in Ukraine. Crimea, in greenhouses everywhere.

Host plants. Polyphagous. 40 species of the Crimean host plants are listed (Livschitz *et al.*, 1972); 94 plant species of 43 families are recorded as host plants in greenhouses of Ukraine (Chumak, 2004a).

Brevipalpus olearius Sayed, 1950

Livschitz & Mitrofanov (1967, 1973), Mitrofanov & Strunkova (1979).

Distribution in Ukraine. Crimea.

Host plant. *Olea* sp.

Notes: causes mosaic patterns on leaves.

Brevipalpus phoenicis (Geijskes, 1939)

Chumak (2000, 2003).

Distribution in Ukraine. In greenhouses of Kyiv and Kharkiv.

Host plants. *Phoenix roebelenii* O'Brien, *Washingtonia filifera* H. Wendl ex Wats, *W. robusta* H. Wendl.

***Brevipalpus recki* Livschitz & Mitrofanov, 1967**

Livschitz & Mitrofanov (1967, 1968), Mitrofanov (1973: *Tauripalpus recki*), Mitrofanov & Strunkova (1979).

Distribution in Ukraine. Crimea.

Host plants. *Quercus pubescens* Willd., *Quercus* sp. (Fagaceae), *Rubus* (Rosaceae), *Inula vulgaris* Trevis. (Asteraceae).

***Brevipalpus russulus* (Boisduval, 1867)**

Livschitz & Mitrofanov (1967), Mitrofanov & Strunkova (1979), Chumak (2000, 2003, 2004a, b: *Hystripalpus russulus*).

Distribution in Ukraine. Crimea, in greenhouses, everywhere.

Host plants. Cactaceae.

Notes: often gives outbreaks and spoils the decorative appearance of plants.

***Brevipalpus thelycraniae* Livschitz & Mitrofanov, 1967**

Livschitz & Mitrofanov (1967), Mitrofanov & Strunkova (1979: *Cenopalpus (Cenopalpus) thelycraniae*).

Distribution in Ukraine. Crimea.

Host plant. *Cornus sanguinea* L.

Cenopalpus Pritchard & Baker, 1958

***Cenopalpus carpini* (Livschitz & Mitrofanov, 1967)**

Livschitz & Mitrofanov (1967: *Brevipalpus carpini*), Livschitz & Mitrofanov (1973), Mitrofanov & Strunkova (1979: *Cenopalpus (Cenopalpus) carpini*).

Distribution in Ukraine. Crimea.

Host plant. *Carpinus orientalis* Mill.

Notes: often gives outbreaks and causes mosaic patterns on leaves.

***Cenopalpus lineola* (Canestrini & Fanzago, 1876)**

Livschitz & Mitrofanov (1967: *Brevipalpus lineola*), Livschitz & Mitrofanov (1973), Mitrofanov (1973a: *Cenopalpus (Cenopalpoides) lineola*), Mitrofanov et al. (1975: *Cenopalpus (Cenopalpoides) lineola*), Mitrofanov & Strunkova (1979: *Cenopalpus (Cenopalpoides) lineola*).

Distribution in Ukraine. Crimea.

Host plants. *Pinus nigra pallasiana* (Lamb.) Holmboe, *Pinus* sp.

Notes: at bases of pine needles.

***Cenopalpus longirostris* (Livschitz & Mitrofanov, 1967)**

Livschitz & Mitrofanov (1967, 1973: *Brevipalpus longirostris*), Mitrofanov & Strunkova (1979: *Cenopalpus (Cenopalpus) longirostris*).

Distribution in Ukraine. Crimea.

Host plants. *Quercus pubescens* Willd., *Quercus* sp.

Notes: often as a pest along with *Brevipalpus recki*.

***Cenopalpus mespili* (Livschitz & Mitrofanov, 1967)**

Livschitz & Mitrofanov (1967: *Brevipalpus mespili*), Livschitz & Mitrofanov (1973), Mitrofanov & Strunkova (1979: *Cenopalpus (Cenopalpus) mespili*).

Distribution in Ukraine. Crimea.

Host plants. *Mespilus* sp., *Cotoneaster* sp., *Malus* sp., *Crataegus* sp.

Notes: usual pest of trees and shrubs at the Southern coast of Crimea.

***Cenopalpus piger* Wainstein, 1960**

Wainstein (1960).

Distribution in Ukraine. Crimea.

Host plants. various fruit trees.

***Cenopalpus pseudospinosus* (Livschitz & Mitrofanov, 1967)**

Livschitz & Mitrofanov (1967: *Brevipalpus pseudospinosus*).

Distribution in Ukraine. Crimea.

Host plant. *Rubus* sp.

***Cenopalpus pulcher* (Canestrini & Fanzago, 1876)**

Livschitz & Mitrofanov (1967: *Brevipalpus pulcher*), Dmitriyev (1969), Voitenko (1969), Livschitz & Mitrofanov (1973), Kruglikov (1985), Mitrofanov & Strunkova (1979), Akimov et al. (1993), Pogrebnnyak (1998).

Distribution in Ukraine. All Ukraine.

Host plants. Rosaceae.

Notes: widespread, however gives outbreaks mostly in southern regions.

***Cenopalpus wainsteini* (Livschitz & Mitrofanov, 1967)**

Livschitz & Mitrofanov (1967: *Brevipalpus wainsteini*), Livschitz & Mitrofanov (1973), Mitrofanov et al. (1975), Mitrofanov & Strunkova (1979: *Cenopalpus (Cenopalpoides) wainsteini*).

Distribution in Ukraine. Crimea.

Host plants. *Pinus* sp.

Notes: causes yellowing of pine needles when given outbreaks.

***Pentamerismus* McGregor, 1949**

***Pentamerismus foliisetis* Livschitz & Mitrofanov, 1967**

Livschitz & Mitrofanov (1967), Mitrofanov et al. (1975), Mitrofanov & Strunkova (1979).

Distribution in Ukraine. Crimea.

Host plants. *Cupressus* sp., *Juniperus* sp., *Platycladus* sp.

Notes: causes decoloration of plant needles.

***Pentamerismus juniperi* (Reck, 1951)**

Livschitz & Mitrofanov (1967, 1973), Mitrofanov et al. (1975), Mitrofanov & Strunkova (1979).

Distribution in Ukraine. Crimea.

Host plants. *Juniperus* sp.

Notes: severely damages host plants in green parks.

***Pentamerismus oregonensis* McGregor, 1949**

Livschitz & Mitrofanov (1967), Mitrofanov et al. (1975: *Oligomerismus oregonensis*), Mitrofanov & Strunkova (1979), Bondareva & Chumak (2020).

Distribution in Ukraine. Crimea, Kherson Region, Kyiv.

Host plants. *Calocedrus decurrens* (Torr.) Florin, *Cupressus* sp., *Juniperus chinensis* L., *J. communis* L., *J. davurica* Pall., *J. excelsa* Bieb., *J. foetidissima* Willd., *J. horizontalis* Moench, *J. x media* Melle, *J. oxycedrus* L., *J. prostrata* Pers., *J. rigida* Siebold & Zucc., *J. sabina* L., *J. scopulorum* Sarg., *J. sibirica* Burgsd., *J. virginiana* L., *J. tuekestanica* Kom., *J. spartan*, *Platycladus* sp., *Thuja* sp.

***Pentamerismus tauricus* Livschitz & Mitrofanov, 1970**

Livschitz & Mitrofanov (1970), Mitrofanov (1973b: *Livschitzia tauricus*), Mitrofanov & Strunkova (1979).

Distribution in Ukraine. Crimea.

Host plant. *Cistus creticus* L.

***Pentamerismus taxi* (Haller, 1877)**

Livschitz & Mitrofanov (1967), Mitrofanov (1973a), Mitrofanov et al. (1975: *Oligomerismus taxi*), Mitrofanov & Strunkova (1979: *Oligomerismus taxi*), Bondareva et al. (2017), Bondareva & Chumak (2018).

Distribution in Ukraine. Crimea, Kyiv.

Host plants. *Taxus baccata* L., *Taxus x media* Rehder 'Hicksii', *Taxus* sp.

Pseudoleptus* Bruyant, 1911**Pseudoleptus graminicola* Mitrofanov & Sharonov, 1983**

Mitrofanov & Sharonov (1983).

Distribution in Ukraine. Crimea (Mys Martjan Reserve).

Host plants. Poaceae.

Tenuipalpus Donnadieu*, 1875**Tenuipalpus arbuti* Mitrofanov & Sharonov, 1983**

Mitrofanov & Sharonov (1983).

Distribution in Ukraine. Crimea.

Host plant. *Arbutus unedo* L.

***Tenuipalpus cheladzeae* Gomelauri, 1960**

Livschitz & Mitrofanov (1967, 1973), Mitrofanov et al. (1975), Mitrofanov & Strunkova (1979).

Distribution in Ukraine. Crimea.

Host plants. *Abies nordmanniana* Spach, *A. firma* Siebold & Zucc., *A. numidica* de Lannoy ex Carrière, *Picea pungens* Engelm, *Taxus baccata* L.

***Tenuipalpus ephedrae* Livschitz & Mitrofanov, 1970**

Livschitz & Mitrofanov (1970), Mitrofanov & Strunkova (1979).

Distribution in Ukraine. Crimea (the coast of Sivash, the vicinity of Chersonesos).

Host plant. *Ephedra distachya* L.

***Tenuipalpus granati* Sayed, 1946**

Livschitz & Mitrofanov (1967, 1973: *Brevipalpus granati*), Mitrofanov (1973b: *Aegyptopalpus granati*), Mitrofanov & Strunkova (1979: *Aegyptopalpus granati*), Chumak (2000, 2003, 2004 a, b: *Aegyptopalpus granati*).

Distribution in Ukraine. Crimea, and in greenhouses of Uzhhorod, Lviv, Kyiv, Dnipro and Odessa.

Host plants. *Cydonia oblonga* Mill., *Punica granatum* L., *Vitis* sp.

***Tenuipalpus kobachidzei* Reck, 1951**

Livschitz & Mitrofanov (1967), Mitrofanov & Strunkova (1979).

Distribution in Ukraine. Crimea.

Host plant. *Calamintha* Mill., *Clematis* sp., *Mentha* sp., *Thymus* sp.

***Tenuipalpus rosae* Kadzhaja, 1955**

Livschitz & Mitrofanov (1967), Mitrofanov (1973b: *Gnathopalpus rosae*), Mitrofanov & Strunkova (1979: *Colopalpus rosae*).

Distribution in Ukraine. Crimea.

Host plant. *Rosa* sp.

***Tenuipalpus tauricus* (Mitrofanov & Strunkova, 1978)**

Mitrofanov & Strunkova (1978: *Gnathopalpus tauricus*), Mitrofanov & Strunkova (1979: *Colopalpus tauricus*).

Distribution in Ukraine. Crimea.

Host plants. *Artemisia* sp., *Cruciata taurica* (Pall.) Ehrend., *Thymus* sp.

References

- Akimov, I.A., Kolodochka, L.A., Pavlitshenko, P.G., Voitenko, A.N., Kulczycki, A.G., Vinnyk, E.N. & Pogrebnyak, S.G. 1993. Industrial orchard mite associations in Ukraine and their structural peculiarities. *Vestnik zoologii*, 6: 48–56. [In Russian]
- Bagdasarian, A.T. 1962. Contribution to the fauna false spider mites from Armenia. *Izvestia Akademii Nauk SSR*, 15 (4): 49–58. [In Russian]
- Beard, J.J., Ochoa, R., Bauchan, G.R., Trice, M.D., Redford, A.J., Walters, T.W. & Mitter, C. 2012. *Flat Mites of the World*. 2nd ed. Ft. Collins, CO, USA: Identification Technology Program, CPHST, PPQ, APHIS, USDA.
- Bondareva, L.M. & Chumak, P.Y. 2018. *Pentamerismus taxi* (Haller, 1877) (Acari: Tenuipalpidae): A New Pest in the Conditions of Kyiv. *Russian Journal of Biological Invasions*, 9 (1): 9–12. DOI: 10.1134/S2075111718010034

- Bondareva, L.M. & Chumak, P.Y. 2020. First finding of *Pentamerismus oregonensis* and its abundance (Acari: Tenuipalpidae) on juniper trees in Kyiv, Ukraine. *Persian journal of acarology*, 9 (3): 299–301. DOI: 10.22073/pja.v9i3.60667
- Bondareva, L.M., Chumak, P.Y. & Bondariev, S.I. 2017. Revealing the Sustainable Population of *Pentamerismus taxi* (Acari, Tenuipalpidae) Outside the Zone of its Natural Habitation in Ukraine. *Vestnik zoologii*, 51 (5): 435–438. DOI: 10.1515/vzoo-2017-0052
- Castro, E.B., Mesa, N.C., Feres, R.J.F., Moraes, G.J.de, Ochoa, R., Beard, J.J. & Demite, P.R. 2020. Tenuipalpidae Database. Available from: <http://www.tenuipalpidae.ibilce.unesp.br> (accessed 25/07/2020).
- Chumak, P.Y. 2000. Tenuipalpidae mites as pests of introduced plants in greenhouses of Ukraine. *Bulletin of Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv. Series Introduction and preservation of plant diversity*, 3: 71–74. [In Ukrainian]
- Chumak, P.Y. 2003. On the Arachnida living in greenhouses of botanical gardens in Ukraine. *Bulletin of Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv. Series Introduction and preservation of plant diversity*, 6: 47–48. [In Ukrainian]
- Chumak, P.Y. 2004a. *Arthropoda in greenhouses of Ukraine and the ecological principles of protection of plants against pests*. K., Publishing and printing center Kyiv University, 1–143. [In Ukrainian]
- Chumak, P.Y. 2004b. *Brevipalpus obovatus* Donn. and biological measures of introduced plants protection from vermin. *Plant introduction*, 4: 83–87. [In Ukrainian]
- Kruglikov, S.A. 1985. *Biocoenotic fundamentals of control measures against phytophagous mites in orchards of steppe and wood-and-steppe of U.S.S.R.* Thesis Ph.D. L: 1–20. [In Russian]
- Livschitz, I.Z. & Mitrofanov, V.I. 1967. *Materials to the cognition of the Acariformes: Tenuipalpidae fauna*. Proceedings Nikitsky Botanic Garden, 39: 1–72. [In Russian]
- Livschitz, I.Z. & Mitrofanov, V.I. 1968. New species of red false spider mites (Acarina, Tetranychoida) from the Crimea and Tadzhikistan. *Revue d'Entomologie de l'URSS*. 47 (3): 671–682. [In Russian]
- Livschitz, I.Z. & Mitrofanov, V.I. 1970. New species of mites (Tenuipalpidae, Acariformes). *Zoologicheskii Zhurnal*, 49: 787–789. [In Russian]
- Livschitz, I.Z. & Mitrofanov, V.I. 1973. Class Arachnida. In: Vasiliev VP (Ed). *Pests of agriculture and forest plantations. V. 1, Pest nematodes, mollusks and arthropods*. K., Urozhay: 128–129. [In Russian with English Abstract]
- Livschitz, I.Z. 1964. Tetranychidae pests of crops (morphology, biology, and control measures. *Thesis Dr. Sc. Trud. Krasn. Znam. Ukrainian Agricultural Academy*. K.: 1–18. [In Russian]
- Livschitz, I.Z., Mitrofanov, V.I. & Vasilyeva, E.A. 1972. On the morphology and biology of *Brevipalpus obovatus* Donnadieu, 1879 (Acariformes, Tenuipalpidae). *Proceedings Nikitsky Botanic Garden*, 61: 65–75. [In Russian]
- Mesa, N.C., Ochoa, R., Welbourn, W.C., Evans, G.A. & Moraes, G.J. 2009. A catalog of Tenuipalpidae Berlese of the world (Acari: Prostigmata). *Zootaxa* 2098: 1–185.
- Mitrofanov, V.I. & Sharonov, A.A. 1983. A contribution to the fauna of plant-feeding mites (Acariformes: Tetranychidae) of Crimea. *Zoologicheskii Zhurnal*, 62: 947–950. [In Russian]
- Mitrofanov, V.I. & Strunkova, Z.I. 1978. A new genus and species of the family Tenuipalpidae (Trombidiformes). *Zoologicheskii Zhurnal*, 52: 1095–1099. [In Russian]
- Mitrofanov, V.I. & Strunkova, Z.I. 1979. *Key to false spider mites. Opredelitel kleschey-ploskotelok*. Dushanbe, Donish: 1–148. [In Russian]
- Mitrofanov, V.I. 1973a. Revision of the subfamily Brevipalpinae (Trombidiformes, Tenuipalpidae). *Zoologicheskii Zhurnal*, 52: 507–512. [In Russian]
- Mitrofanov, V.I. 1973b. Revision of the system of phytophagous mites of the subfamily Tenuiplapinae s. str. (Trombidiformes, Tenuipalpidae). *Zoologicheskii Zhurnal*, 52: 1315–1320. [In Russian]
- Mitrofanov, V.I., Bosenko, L.I. & Bichevskis, M.Y.A. 1975. *Key for the determination of Tetranychidae mites of coniferous trees*. Riga, Zinatne: 1–37. [In Russian]
- Pogrebnyak, S.G. 1998. Orchard acarocomplex in Ukraine. *Zeszyty naukowe ochrona srodowiska*, 2: 83–90. DOI: 10.13140 / RG.2.1.3434.4405
- Tereznikova, E.M. & Chumak, P.Y. 1989. *Protection of flowering and decorative plants against pests*. M., Agropromizdat: 1–127. [In Russian]
- Voitenko, A.N. 1969. *Dendrophilic Tetranychidae mites Polissia of Ukraine*. K.: 1–17. [In Russian with English abstract]
- Wainstein, B.A. 1960. Tetranychoid mites of Kazakhstan (with revision of the family). *Trudy Nauchno-issled. inst. zashchity rastenii Kazakhskoi SSR*, 5: 1–276. [In Russian]